

Studies on Rare Earth Propionates and Chloropropionates

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Propionates, 2-chloropropionates and 2,2-dichloropropionates of Sc^{III}, Y^{III}, La^{III}, Ce^{III} and Dy^{III} were prepared and their thermal behaviour and bonding characteristics studied. While the anhydrous propionates of the lighter rare earths decompose on heating to oxycarbonate and subsequently to oxide, those of the heavy rare earths decompose directly to oxide. 2-Chloropropionates and 2,2-dichloropropionates decompose to oxychloride and subsequently to oxide at higher temperatures. Yttrium chloropropionates resemble lighter rare earths in their thermal behaviour. Infrared spectral studies of these complexes indicate that the metal-ligand bonding is mainly ionic and ionicity is found to be in the order, propionates < 2-chloropropionates < 2,2-dichloropropionates.

In recent years the reactions of rare earths with various carboxylic acids have received considerable attention¹⁻⁸. Thermogravimetric studies have shown that the existence of intermediary products depends markedly on the heating rate and the oxide formation temperatures decrease with increase in the atomic number of the rare earths. Infrared spectral studies of various carboxylates of rare earths⁹⁻¹² have shown that the bonding in these compounds is essentially ionic in nature with slight increase in covalency with increase in atomic number.

The present paper describes the results of our studies on the chloropropionates Sc^{III}, Y^{III}, La^{III}, Ce^{III} and Dy^{III}. For comparative study the data obtained on the propionates are also included.

Experimental

Preparation of compounds: Rare earth (RE), yttrium and scandium propionates and chloropropionates were prepared by dissolving the respective carbonates in the corresponding acids. The carbonates were freshly precipitated by the addition of ammonium carbonate to the nitrate solution and washing free from extraneous ions. The compounds were crystallised from the filtrate and finally dried over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Analysis: All the compounds were analysed for rare earth and ligand contents. Rare earths were determined by precipitating as oxalates followed by ignition to oxide. The ligand content was determined by titrating the liberated acid on passing the aqueous solution of the respective compounds through cation-exchanger in hydrogen form. The molecular weights were calculated from oxide content of the compounds. Water molecules were computed from the above data. The analytical data of representative compounds are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—MOLECULAR COMPOSITION AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF RARE EARTH PROPIONATES AND CHLOROPROPIONATES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)		
	Metal	Ligand	H ₂ O
La(CH ₃ CH ₂ COO) ₃ .1.5H ₂ O	36.2 (36.0)	56.8 (56.5)	7.0 (7.5)
Ce(CH ₃ CH ₂ COO) ₃ .1.5H ₂ O	36.2 (36.3)	56.4 (56.7)	7.4 (7.0)
Dy(CH ₃ CH ₂ COO) ₃ .1.5H ₂ O	39.6 (39.8)	53.5 (53.6)	6.9 (6.6)
Y(CH ₃ CH ₂ COO) ₃ .H ₂ O	26.8 (26.5)	65.6 (65.4)	7.6 (8.1)
Sc(CH ₃ CH ₂ COO) ₃ .1.5H ₂ O	15.3 (15.4)	75.4 (75.3)	9.3 (9.3)
La(CH ₃ CHClCOO) ₃ .2H ₂ O	27.8 (27.9)	64.7 (64.8)	7.5 (7.3)
Ce(CH ₃ CHClCOO) ₃ .2H ₂ O	27.9 (28.0)	64.5 (64.7)	7.6 (7.3)
Dy(CH ₃ CHClCOO) ₃ .2H ₂ O	31.3 (31.2)	61.4 (62.0)	7.3 (6.8)
Y(CH ₃ CHClCOO) ₃ .2H ₂ O	19.8 (19.9)	72.5 (72.0)	7.7 (8.1)
Sc(CH ₃ CHClCOO) ₃ .2H ₂ O	11.0 (11.1)	80.2 (79.9)	8.8 (9.0)
La(CH ₃ CCl ₂ COO) ₃ .H ₂ O	23.9 (23.3)	73.2 (73.0)	2.9 (3.2)
Ce(CH ₃ CCl ₂ COO) ₃ .H ₂ O	23.9 (24.0)	73.5 (72.9)	2.6 (3.1)
Dy(CH ₃ CCl ₂ COO) ₃ .H ₂ O	26.6 (26.3)	70.4 (70.2)	3.0 (3.0)
Y(CH ₃ CCl ₂ COO) ₃ .H ₂ O	17.0 (16.7)	79.5 (79.9)	3.5 (3.4)
Sc(CH ₃ CCl ₂ COO) ₃ .H ₂ O	9.5 (9.2)	87.4 (87.1)	3.1 (3.7)

The thermal behaviour of the compounds in air was studied using Stanton self-recording thermobalance. The heating rate was maintained at 4°/min. The composition of the compounds formed at various stages was evaluated from the weight losses, and later confirmed by chemical analysis for the metal and carbonate content^{1,3} in propionates, and metal and chlorine content^{1,4} in chloropropionates. In addition, formation of anhydrous compounds

was confirmed by infrared spectra. DTA curves were recorded with a recorder span of 0.5 mV.

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 21 spectrophotometer using nujol mull in the range $4\ 000 - 200\ \text{cm}^{-1}$.

Results and Discussion

Propionates of La, Ce, Pr and Nd melt at 252, 238, 218 and 204°, respectively, whereas the propionates of the rest of the rare earths, Sc and Y and chloropropionates of rare earths, Sc and Y decomposed before melting.

The thermograms of La, Dy, Y, Ce and Sc propionates and chloropropionates are given in Figs. 1

and 2. The thermal behaviour of lighter rare earths (LRE *i.e.* La—Gd) and heavy rare earths (HRE *i.e.* Tb—Lu) propionates and chloropropionates is similar to that of La and Dy, respectively, the

Fig. 1. Thermogravimetric curves for decomposition of (A) lanthanum propionate, (B) 2-chloropropionate, (C) 2,2-dichloropropionate; and (D) dysprosium propionate, (E) 2-chloropropionate, (F) 2,2-dichloropropionate,

Fig. 2. Thermogravimetric curves for decomposition of (A) cerium propionate, (B) 2-chloropropionate, (C) 2,2-dichloropropionate; (F) yttrium propionate, (D) 2-chloropropionate, (E) 2,2-dichloropropionate; (I) scandium propionate, (G) 2-chloropropionate, (H) 2,2-dichloropropionate.

major difference being the temperatures at which the different products are formed. The data indicate that the loss of water begins at 80° and the propionates of RE and Y and chloropropionates of HRE and Y give stable anhydrous compounds at 180° whereas the other propionates decompose simultaneously.

DTA (Fig. 3) of La, Gd and Dy propionates showed endothermic peaks in the temperature range

75–150, 85–150 and 95–150°, respectively. Similarly, the DTA of dichloropropionates of La, Gd and Dy showed endothermic peaks in the range 115–170, 90–150 and 80–150° respectively. This

Fig. 3. DTA curves of propionates of (A) gadolinium, (B) lanthanum, (C) dysprosium, 2,2-dichloropropionates of (D) dysprosium, (E) gadolinium, (F) lanthanum.

step corresponds to loss of water. The endothermic peak at 255° in La propionate is caused by its fusion, which fairly agrees with the melting point of La propionate determined separately. The weight losses correspond to the loss of water molecules (Figs. 1 and 2) and the infrared spectra of these compounds showed absence of absorption band for water molecules confirming the formation of anhydrous compounds.

Further DTA data (Fig. 3) show that (i) Gd propionate and 2,2-dichloropropionate differ from other rare earth propionates and 2,2-dichloropropionates of LRE by losing water in two steps, an observation similar to acetates¹⁵ indicating that part of the water molecules are firmly held (compared to the rest) and (ii) HRE chloropropionates

lose water in two steps (instead of one as shown by the thermograms) yielding anhydrous compounds. The anhydrous and hydrated propionates and chloropropionates decompose to oxycarbonate and oxychloride, respectively. The absence of oxycarbonate formation in HRE propionates is contrary to the observations of Loginova *et al.*¹². The carbonate content of the products of Ce and HRE propionates at temperatures at which the weight losses in the thermogram correspond to the formation of oxycarbonate has been found to be too low (with metal—CO₂ molar ratios around 12:1 for Ce and 5:1 for Dy) to predict oxycarbonate-formation. The analysis of the thermally stable products formed in LRE propionates (350–450°) and RE chloropropionates (500–600°) give metal—CO₂ ratio 2:1 and RE—Cl ratio 1:1, indicating formation of oxycarbonate and oxychloride, respectively. Trichloride formation has not been observed in thermal decomposition of 2-chloro- and 2,2-dichloropropionates as is observed in dichloroacetates¹⁶. However, from RE—Cl values in the decomposition products in 2-chloropropionates (275–325°, M—Cl 1:2+3% C) and 2,2-dichloropropionates (300–350°, M—Cl 1:2.5+5% C) formation and simultaneous decomposition of RE trichlorides can be predicted.

The DTA curves were recorded in air using platinum sample holders. It is likely that the decomposition peaks of anhydrous propionates to oxycarbonate, recorded in the temperature range 260–425° are complicated involving decomposition of the compound together with the burning up of the carbonaceous products. The latter process is highly exothermic and the exothermic nature of the peaks recorded in the present studies are probably due to the predominance of the heat of the reaction over that of the decomposition. Similarly, the exothermic peaks observed in the DTA of dichloropropionates of La, Gd and Dy in the temperature range 380–530° represent formation of oxychloride. On further heating to higher temperatures the oxycarbonates and oxychlorides slowly get converted to oxide. The temperature at which this change occurs decreases with the basicity of the metal in lanthanides. The temperature of decomposition of the propionates and chloropropionates with formation of oxycarbonate and oxychloride are not appreciably different for different rare earths. Similarly, no regular trend is observed from propionates to chloropropionates. The decomposition temperature for the oxycarbonate is much lower compared to the oxychloride. In the case of LRE chloropropionates, the conversion of oxychloride is slower compared to the HRE. The oxychlorides derived from 2,2-dichloropropionates of La, Pr and Nd are even stable at 1000° and are not converted to oxide, an observation which is similar to La trichloroacetate¹⁷, whereas for the rest of the REs the oxide formation is complete around 800°. Further, the oxide formation temperatures are lower for propionates as compared to chloropropionates. Cerium oxide formation takes

TABLE 2—INFRARED BAND (cm^{-1}) OF METAL PROPIONATES, 2-CHLOROPROPIONATES AND 2,2-DICHLOROPROPIONATES

Element	Propionates			2-Chloropropionates			2,2-Dichloropropionates		
	ν_{asym} OCO	ν_{sym} OCO	$\Delta\nu$	ν_{asym} OCO	ν_{sym} OCO	$\Delta\nu$	ν_{asym} OCO	ν_{sym} OCO	$\Delta\nu$
Na	1 563	1 370	193	1 580	1 380	200	1 640	1 378	262
La	1 550	1 380	170	1 560	1 385	175	1 612	1 380	232
Ce	1 550	1 382	168	1 573	1 380	193	1 600	1 375	225
Pr	1 545	1 380	165	1 580	1 370	210	1 608	1 380	228
Nd	1 550	1 380	170	1 575	1 375	200	1 610	1 380	230
Gd	1 553	1 379	174	1 570	1 375	195	1 605	1 380	225
Tb	1 560	1 378	182	1 585	1 380	205	1 608	1 378	230
Dy	1 562	1 378	184	1 580	1 380	200	1 618	1 365	253
Lu	1 568	1 382	186	1 575	1 384	191	1 620	1 380	240
Y	1 565	1 380	185	1 590	1 388	202	1 620	1 378	242
Sc	1 525	1 375	150	1 558	1 370	188	1 600	1 380	220

$$\Delta\nu = \nu_{\text{asym}} \text{OCO} - \nu_{\text{sym}} \text{OCO}$$

place at very low temperatures compared to the rest of the RE propionates which may be attributed to the stability of tetravalent oxide. However, the oxide formation temperature in Ce increases from propionate to 2,2-dichloropropionate. Yttrium 2-chloro- and 2,2-dichloro-propionates resemble the LRE compounds, even at 1000° a mixture of oxide and oxychloride was obtained. Y and Sc propionates differ from the rest of the propionates by decomposing to oxycarbonate instead of oxide in the temperature range studied. However, on prolonged heating at 1000° (for ~30 min) these oxycarbonates slowly get converted to oxide. This may be attributed to the fact that Sc and Y have more affinity towards carbonate as compared to La.

The infrared data are given in Table 2. These assignments are based on the work of Jakobsen *et al.*¹⁸. The data for sodium compounds are also included for comparison. The data show that as compared to sodium propionate the bands due to symmetric stretching modes of COO^- in the rare earth ones are slightly shifted to higher wavenumbers, whereas the antisymmetric stretching mode shifted considerably to lower wavenumbers in LRE propionates, while there is slight shift to higher wavenumbers in the compounds with HRE. This is true in the case of 2-chloropropionates also. In 2,2-dichloropropionates, the shift in asym COO^- to lower wavenumbers is more as compared to HRE. These observations suggest that the structure of LRE compounds may be different from those of HRE as was observed in acetates⁹. The frequency separation between the antisymmetric and symmetric COO stretching frequencies ($\Delta\nu$) varies in the range 150–186, 175–210 and 220–253 for RE propionates, 2-chloropropionates and 2,2-dichloropropionates, respectively. These results indicate that bonding is essentially ionic. In the rare earth series, with the decrease in the radius of metal ion, one would expect an increase in the degree of covalent character of Ln–O bond. However $\Delta\nu$ values do not show a gradual variation.

The absorption maxima occurring at 1 563 and 1 370 cm^{-1} in sodium propionate, 1 580 and 1 380

cm^{-1} in sodium 2-chloropropionate and 1 640 and 1 378 cm^{-1} in sodium 2,2-dichloropropionate have been assigned to antisymmetric and symmetric vibrations of the carboxylic group. Due to chlorine substitution $\nu_{\text{sym}} \text{COO}$ is affected slightly; however, $\nu_{\text{asym}} \text{COO}$ shifts to high wavenumbers. The same trend is observed in RE, Sc and Y compounds also. Chlorine has an electron withdrawing effect and as such ionicity increases with its substitution. It is therefore evident that as the ionicity increases from propionates to dichloropropionates the $\nu_{\text{asym}} \text{COO}$ shifts to higher wavenumbers. The $\Delta\nu$ increases in the order, propionates < 2-chloropropionates < 2,2-dichloropropionates. Infrared spectra of Y propionate and chloropropionates are similar to HRE. Sc propionate, 2-chloropropionate and 2,2-dichloropropionate are covalent compared to the corresponding sodium and RE compounds.

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